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Manufacturing ScCeSZ/GDC Electrolyte Composite Layers for IT-SOFC by Reverse Aqueous Tape Casting

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Abstract

Recent advances in solid oxide cell (SOC) technology have been focusing on the materials so they to increase the power capability at reduced operating temperatures, from now typically around 800°C to below 700°C. In light of this, this work investigates the potential of a NiO/10Sc1CeSZ anode, and 10Sc1CeSZ electrolyte, with an La_{0.6}Sr_{0.4}Co_{0.2}Fe_{0.8} Oxide (LSCF) cathode and Gd_{0.2}Ce_{0.8} Oxide (GDC) barrier layer. It has previously been difficult to manufacture these cells via tape casting because the GDC barrier layer delaminates from the electrolyte layer upon high temperature sintering. This is due to thermal expansion coefficient (TEC) mismatch. Here, the capability of using reverse aqueous tape casting to manufacture anode supported cells (ASC) using a multi-layer technique is proven. GDC barrier layer, new electrolyte/barrier layer, electrolyte layer, anode functional layer (AFL) and anode substrate (AS) are tape cast effectively. The composite layer allows for a gradual transition from electrolyte to barrier layer eliminating the harsh step-change of TEC and, therefore, delamination upon sintering. Multiple cells were tested between 650 and 800°C in a hydrogen/nitrogen mixture on the anode and air on the cathode side to yield a maximum power density of 0.4 W/cm².

Introduction

In order for solid oxide fuel cells (SOFC) to become fully commercial, it is important to reduce the production costs and increase the lifetime. Research over the last decade has focused on reducing the degradation of the materials [1], optimising microstructure [2,3], dealing with fuel flexibility [4,5], and reducing the operating temperature from over 800°C to below 700°C in order to minimise thermally activated degradation effects and thermal stresses [6–8]. At high temperatures, the formation of SrZrO₃ insulating layers between the electrolyte and the cathode hinders the movement of oxygen ions across the electrolyte. The addition of a GDC barrier layer can stop Sr migration [9]. However, there are difficulties in manufacturing this barrier layer by the tape casting technique [10], due to the mismatch of thermal expansion coefficients, which leads to the GDC layer delaminating from the electrolyte upon high temperature sintering. In 2017, Menranjani et al. [11] discussed the impossibility of creating a bi-layer electrolyte by depositing a YSZ layer onto GDC due to the shrinkage mismatch. Furthermore, preliminary studies on the residual stresses of YSZ and GDC by Atkinson et al. [12] identified how the significant TEC of GDC weakened the electrolyte upon cooling down from the sintering temperature.

Screen-printing and physical vapour deposition (PVD) have been used in an attempt to combat this issue, however, they require additives that can reduce cell performance, are more costly, or are more time consuming in comparison to tape casting [13]. In 2013, Song et al. [14] found that the addition of a sintering aid to a screen printed GDC layer produced a dense barrier layer at higher sintering temperatures, but yielded a reduced electrochemical performance (0.385 Wcm⁻²) compared to a cell fabricated without any sintering aid (0.86 Wcm⁻²). In 2018, a research group demonstrated the ability of introducing a composite layer between a YSZ electrolyte and a GDC barrier layer through the magnetron sputtering technique. They manufactured graded deposits of GDC and YSZ to obtain cells that yielded 0.94 Wcm⁻², compared to their screen printed cells, 1.2 Wcm⁻², however, the degradation rate for these magnetron sputtered cells was very high (18%/1000 h) due to poor adhesion of the sputtered layer [9].

1. Scientific Approach

In this work, aqueous tape casting has been chosen as the method of fabrication because of its cost-effective and well-established method of producing homogeneous green tapes, suitable for industrial production without harmful solvents. The reverse tape casting approach established by Menzler et al. [15] was used in this work and adapted to include a tape cast barrier layer. The GDC layer was cast first, followed by the composite layer, the electrolyte layer, and the anode functional layer (AFL), each layer being oven-dried in between casting at 70°C for 15 minutes. This was followed by casting the anode support (AS) and a final drying at 30°C for 24 hours to produce a homogeneous green tape. To densify the half cells, they were co-sintered at 1000°C and then fully sintered at 1400°C. LSCF cathode ink was painted on the GDC side of the half cell and sintered at 975°C. Fig. 1 illustrates the tape casting and cathode printing steps in sequence.

Fig. 1. Order of casting layers in five-layer anode-supported SOC manufacturing. Scheme adopted from [16].

2. Experimental Details

To produce a thin green tape, a Compact Tape Casting Film Coater with dryer and vacuum bed (MTI Corporation, USA) was used. The speed and gap height of the doctor blade was variable to allow for different thickness of green tapes. The cells fabricated and tested in this work were based on NiO/ScCeSZ material sets and the formulation based upon previous work by Arifin et al. [17]. Table 1 lists the materials used in the tape casting procedure with their physical properties.

Table 1. Materials used in the anode supported composite cells.

Material	Function	d ₅₀ Particle Size (µm)	Supplier
NiO	Anode Layers (AFL and AS)	1- 2	Hart Materials, UK
10Sc1CeSZ	Electrolyte	0.8- 1	DKKK, Japan
10GDC	Barrier layer	0.6-1.4	Fuel Cell Materials, U.S.
LSCF	Cathode	0.9	Praxair, U.S.

For the anode substrate, the slurry consisted of 10ScCeSZ pre-calcined at 900°C for 5 hours, with as-received NiO powder in a weight ratio of 65:35 (NiO:10ScCeSZ). Solvent (water), dispersant (Dispex, BASF), cermet powders and pore former (tapioca starch) were mixed together using spherical and cylindrical ZrO₂ beads, and homogenised at 120 rpm for 24 hours. The anode functional layer consisted of a 65:35 mixture of as-received NiO and as-received ScCeSZ powder, mixed together with the same solvent, and homogenised at 120 rpm for 24 hours. Binders, plasticisers I and II and antifoam were

added to each slurry and the mixture rolled for a further 12 h at 70 rpm. To eliminate any air bubbles, both slurries were filtered and de-gassed for 24 h, followed by a phase of 50 rpm slow-roll for 2 h to ensure a homogeneous mixture.

Table 2. Composition of anode layers.

Materials	Function	Composition (wt%)	
		AFL	AS
NiO	Electronic phase	35.8	35.8
ScCeSZ	Ionic phase	19.3	19.3
Tapioca starch	Pore former	-	1.5
BASF Displex Ultra 4404®	Dispersant	1.0	1.0
Water	Solvent	35.4	29.9
Antifoam 204	Antifoam	0.2	0.2
PVA	Binder	4.1	5.4
PEG 200	Plasticiser I	2.7	3.45
Glycerol	Plasticiser II	1.4	3.45

The compositions for the electrolyte, barrier and composite layers are presented in Table 3. First, the solvent, dispersant, binder, anti-foam, and plasticiser were mixed together at 120 rpm for 24 hours. More binder, de-foamer, and the corresponding layer material powder were added and mixed for at least 4 hours at 120 rpm. The slurries were filtered and degassed for 1 hour to eliminate any gas bubbles.

Table 3. Composition of electrolyte, barrier and composite layers.

Materials	Function	Composition (wt%)		
		Barrier layer	Composite layer	Electrolyte
Water	Solvent	28	28	28
WB4101	Binder	19.3	19.3	19.3
DS001	Dispersant	2.0	2.0	2.0
DF002	Antifoam	0.4	0.4	0.4
PL005	Plasticiser	0.5	0.5	0.5
ScCeSZ	Ionic phase	-	24.9	49.8
GDC	Barrier layer	49.8	24.9	-

The GDC slurry was tape cast onto a thin polyester carrier film first, followed by the composite layer, then the electrolyte layer, and the AFL (Fig. 1). After tape casting, each single layer was dried in an oven at 70°C. Finally, the AS was tape cast on top of the AFL and the green tape dried in an oven at 30°C overnight. Cells were cut from the dried green tape using a hydraulic press and a circular die of diameter 40 mm. Cells were sintered at

1400°C for four hours with an organic burnout stage at 550°C, resulting in dense button half-cells with a diameter of 30 mm.

2.1 Cathode Ink Preparation

To prepare the cathode ink, LSCF (supplier Praxair) and GDC (supplier Fuel Cell Materials) were combined in a 50:50 wt% ratio. An ink vehicle (Fuel Cell Materials) was added to the powder to make an ink with a solid loading of 22.8 wt%. LSCF ink was made by mixing LSCF powder with the ink vehicle to receive a solid loading of 25.18 wt%. Both inks were homogenised using a triple roll mill (EXAKT).

2.2 Characterisation

The morphology of the cells was characterised by scanning electron microscopy (SEM) using a Hitachi table-top microscope TM3030Plus. Both cross-section and surface morphology micrographs were taken to examine the microstructure. Image analysis was used to determine the thickness of each layer and the particle size. Energy dispersive x-ray (EDX) images were taken at 15 kV and BSE mode to identify the elemental distribution throughout the cell. Particle size analysis after sintering was determined using ImageJ software. The density and porosity of the half cells were analysed by an AccuPyc II 1340 (Micromeritics) gas pycnometer using helium as the displacement medium. Three purges, followed by three readings for each sample were used to get average density and porosity values. AC impedance measurements were carried out with a Solartron 1470 E and 1455 FRA, sweeping from 0.01 Hz to 10 kHz at 0.7 V, 0.5V and at -0.001 A (near OCV) with an amplitude of 20 mV.

Table 4. Details of the differences in layers using the multi-layer manufacturing technique.

Name	GDC (μm)	Composite (μm)	Electrolyte (μm)	Total (μm)
Cell 333	7.0	7.0	7.5	21.5

Table 4 illustrates the tape casting process of each layer and the relative layer thickness. The label denotes the gap height of the doctor blade used when tape casting, for example, Cell 333 used a gap height of 3 μm for each layer. The AFL and AS layer thickness were approximately 30 μm and 500 μm , respectively.

The composite cells of Ni-ScCeSZ were fabricated into full cells with LSCF cathodes painted onto the GDC barrier layer, resulting in an active area of 2 cm^2 , and sintered at 975°C. The cells were placed in the testing rig, and heated at 5°C/min to 800°C, upon reaching which they were reduced overnight in hydrogen. Two cells underwent initial characterisation at 800°C, with a 3:1 H₂:N₂ flow to the fuel electrode and air to the oxygen electrode.

3. Results

Fig. 2 presents the SEM micrograph of a cell after sintering at 1400°C for 4 hours. The dense electrolyte and the gradual transition to the barrier layer can be clearly seen, with no cracks or delamination from the GDC barrier layer present after sintering, confirming the ability of this multi-layer method to produce robust cells.

Fig. 2. SEM micrograph of the composite layer cross-section of Cell 333, after sintering for 4 hours at 1400°C.

Fig. 3. Performance of Cell 333: Ni-ScCeSZ composite cell prepared by five-layer tape casting tested between 600 and 800°C.

To investigate their potential as SOCs, the manufactured Ni-ScCeSZ cells were tested between 650 and 800°C. Fig. 3. shows a polarisation curve of a Cell333 performance, which can be compared to Ni-ScCeSZ cells previously manufactured in our laboratory, with power densities of 0.39 Wcm⁻² at 750°C and Ni-YSZ cells with a power density of 0.53 Wcm⁻² at 800°C [17].

The area specific resistance (ASR) for the Ni-ScCeSZ cell tested at 700°C was 1.29 Ωcm², and the ASR for Ni-ScCeSZ tested at 800°C was 0.57 Ωcm². The results confirm that ScCeSZ cells tape cast in this novel five-layer technique are perfectly suitable for IT-SOFC applications.

Electrochemical impedance spectroscopy results in Table 5 reveal the resistivity of the whole cell and breaks this further down into electrochemical reactions (high frequency

contributions) and electrode reactions (low frequency contributions). The equivalent circuit used for fitting EIS data to calculate resistances was R_s - R_1Q_1 - R_2Q_2 , where R_s was the ohmic resistance and RQ was a parallel circuit consisting of a resistor and constant phase element, similar to models used by other researchers [18,19]. The impedance results revealed the lowest polarisation resistance for the Ni-ScCeSZ cell at 800°C (0.16 Ωcm^2).

The ASR and internal resistance values are slightly higher than state of the art cells, however, this work aimed to prove that the method of adding another layer to the cell via tape casting, is a legitimate approach in cell manufacturing to minimise cost and maximise output. Further work will ensue to optimise this process to reduce resistances and increase cell performance.

Table 5. Cell resistances close to OCV for Ni-ScCeSZ composite cells at 700°C and 800°C.

T (°C)	R_s (Ωcm^2)	$Q_1(\text{Fcm}^{-1})$	n	R_1 (Ωcm^2)	$Q_2(\text{Fcm}^{-1})$	n	R_2 (Ωcm^2)	R_p (Ωcm^2)
NiSSZ 700	0.69	0.012	0.59	0.58	0.47	0.99	0.093	0.67
NiSSZ 800	0.42	0.0042	0.91	0.081	0.97	0.66	0.078	0.16

3.3 Conclusions

The addition of an ScCeSZ-GDC composite layer in the tape casting fabrication of Ni-ScCeSZ SOCs has been proven. It has been possible to manufacture these layers, which successfully adhere to the electrolyte and GDC barrier layer for LSCF cathode cells, without delamination of the GDC barrier layer upon sintering.

After the functionality of the layer was established, these cells were electrochemically tested in a hydrogen/nitrogen mix to yield power densities of 0.40 Wcm^{-2} at 800 °C. This can be compared with cells previously manufactured: Ni-ScCeSZ resulting in 0.39 Wcm^{-2} at 750°C and Ni-YSZ cells with a power density of 0.53 Wcm^{-2} at 800°C.

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